

MANAGEMENT OF STUDENT COOPERATIVE-BASED EDUCATION FINANCING IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received May 21,2024 Revised Jun 10, 2024 Accepted Jun 17, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Financing Management, Student Cooperative, Education</p>	<p>The review of this research is motivated by education financing in the financing management of the Sidoklumpuk State Elementary School cooperative which can benefit the continuity of educational activities at the school. The purpose of this research is to find out the shape of the system for managing finance in the cooperative that can be benefited by the school community such as purchasing books, learning equipment, or repairing facilities and providing loans with low interest to students and staff for those who have financial difficulties. The method used is a qualitative method that focuses on the management of student cooperative-based education financing in public elementary schools. The research data used observation, interviews and documentation studies. The results of the study show that the benefits and implementation of financing in school cooperatives can be used well by school community. If in the system there is a lack of understanding and managerial skills among students and school staff. Then training is needed for staff or teachers who are responsible so that it can be used with a good managerial system.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-acces article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

Effective education financing plays an important role in improving the quality of education in Indonesia. In this context, school finance serves as an indispensable source of funds to equip learning facilities and infrastructure, improve teachers' welfare and implement supervision programs. Effective education finance management can achieve educational goals by managing school finances through management functions such as planning, bookkeeping, financial use, recording, monitoring and accountability which are expected to create effective and efficient school financial governance [1].

Effective education financing is also needed to improve the quality of education. One way to improve the quality of education is to pay attention to the national education standards that apply in Indonesia, including financing standards. Education financing is used for operational needs, salaries, employee welfare, improving teaching and learning activities, maintaining and procuring facilities and infrastructure, and improving teachers' professional abilities. Thus, the teaching and learning process can run effectively and efficiently, and improve educational performance [2].

Effective education financing means that the management of education funds is carried out efficiently and effectively to achieve the expected educational goals. In the context of education, education costs must be managed effectively to achieve good school quality. The teaching and learning process will improve if the objectives to be achieved meet the requirements. Effective education financing includes the stages of education fund management that involve planning, budgeting, implementation, monitoring and accountability. Thus, effectively managed education costs can help improve the quality of education and achieve the expected educational goals [3].

Student cooperatives can serve as one of the sources of funds for education financing, especially in schools that have active student cooperative programs. In some studies, student cooperatives have shown effective and efficient results in increasing education funding sources. For example, student cooperatives can help increase school revenue by selling products made by students, which can be used to improve the quality of education. Thus, student cooperatives can be an effective and efficient source of funds in supporting educational activities [4].

The need for education financing in primary schools is very important to ensure the continuity of effective and efficient educational activities. Financing education in primary schools involves not only the expenditure of funds for operational costs, but also to ensure the quality of education provided. The financing needs of education in primary schools include costs for facilities, costs for curriculum development, costs for human resource development and costs for educational infrastructure development. In addition, education financing is also needed to ensure the affordability of education for all students, including those with limited economic means [5].

Financing education in primary schools also requires transparency and accountability. This can be achieved by conducting effective financial management, including the appropriate and efficient use of funds. In addition, financial management should also involve various parties, such as teachers, parents and school community members, to ensure that the educational needs of primary schools are met effectively and efficiently. Thus, financing education in primary schools can help improve the quality of education and increase students' awareness of the importance of education [6].

SD Negeri Sidoklumpuk is one of the public elementary schools located in Sidoarjo sub-district. This school is one of the public primary schools that has been running a student cooperative business for quite a long time. The student cooperative of

SDN Sidoklumpuk contributes significantly to the management of education financing by providing an additional source of income for the school and offering affordable financial services to students and staff. Through effective management of the cooperative, the school can generate funds from various business activities such as the canteen, bookstore and facility rentals. The profits earned can be used to support various educational needs, such as the purchase of books, learning equipment or facility improvements. In addition, school cooperatives can also provide low-interest loans to students and staff, helping them overcome financial difficulties that may hinder the teaching and learning process. Thus, school cooperatives not only support the financial sustainability of the school, but also contribute to the well-being of the school community as a whole.

METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach that examines the management of education financing at SDN Sidoklumpuk Sidoarjo. Data collection techniques used observation, interviews and documentation studies. Data analysis in this study was carried out by categorizing data and interpreting data. This research offers an alternative in managing education financing in public elementary schools by maximizing external funding sources from student cooperative business results. So this technique is also used to find out the causes of behavior. Documentation study is a data collection technique by studying various documents that can be used as data, such as notes, reports, work programs, and others. And there is a reference to interaction analysis, where the data reduction and data presentation components are carried out simultaneously with the data collection process and flow together. After the data is collected, the analysis components (data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing) interact [7].

As well as the approach used in this research is a qualitative approach. According to Bogdan and Taylor in stating a qualitative approach is a research procedure that produces descriptive information in the form of written or spoken words from people and behaviors that can be observed [8]. So this research method collects all data - data from the results of interviews and written down in a report or notes and documentation from the results of observations at SDN Sidoklumpuk Sidoarjo school.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Condition of the Research Object

SDN Sidoklumpuk Sidoarjo is one of the public primary schools in the Sidoarjo sub-district, located at Jalan Monginsidi no.23, Sidoklumpuk Village. This school is a government school that uses the national curriculum from the Department of Education and Culture.

Currently SDN Sidoklumpuk has a school building with details of 16 local classrooms, 1 teacher's room, 1 principal's room, 1 computer laboratory, 1 prayer room, 1 UKS, 1 library room, 1 student cooperative and 2 school canteens. All facilities and

infrastructure of SDN Sidoklumpuk are quite good and complete enough for students to use. Starting from the infrastructure used for teaching and learning activities to extracurricular activities. The number of educators and education personnel at this school is also adequate with the number of classes and students. There are 24 class teachers, 8 subject teachers, 4 extracurricular teachers, 1 security guard and 1 school gardener.

B. Description of Student Cooperative-Based Financing Management System

School cooperatives are cooperatives consisting of students from elementary schools, junior high schools, senior high schools, boarding schools, and other educational institutions of the same level. School cooperatives as a support for government development programs in the economic sector, through cooperative education programs in schools, foster school cooperatives and cooperative awareness among students, foster a sense of responsibility, discipline and also school cooperatives are used as a means to meet student needs, especially the needs of school equipment [9].

Student Cooperatives can help students in developing social skills such as cooperation, communication, and time management. In addition, student cooperatives can also help students in developing character traits such as responsibility, discipline, and concern for the community. Student Cooperatives can also be used as a means to improve the welfare of students and the community, and help build the national economic order. In some cases, student cooperatives are also used as a means to meet the needs of students, such as school equipment needs, and help improve the performance of staff and the welfare of students and cooperative members [6].

This is the case at SDN Sidoklumpuk, where there is a Student Cooperative that has been established for several years and whose existence cannot be underestimated. The Student Cooperative of SDN Sidoklumpuk is able to become a source of external funds for financing education at the school. The organizational structure of the Student Cooperative at SDN Sidoklumpuk contains the principal as the person in charge, the daily management consists of 3 teachers and 1 person as the main treasurer.

The establishment of this student cooperative aims at skill development by helping students build social skills such as cooperation, communication, and time management. By participating in cooperative activities, students can improve their ability to work with others and manage complex projects. In addition, Student Cooperatives can also be useful as a means to develop students' character such as responsibility, discipline, and caring. By participating in cooperative activities, students can increase their awareness of the importance of cooperation and responsibility in achieving goals. Thus, the role of student cooperatives in education is very important in improving students' abilities academically and non-academically, as well as increasing social awareness and concern for the community.

The cooperative at SDN Sidoklumpuk provides school supplies for students such as stationery, uniforms, hats, ties, socks and so on. In addition, the cooperative also

provides snacks and drinks that are sold to the entire school community. Some teachers and guardians also play a role in the procurement of food and soft drinks by leaving food or drinks made by themselves.

From the proceeds of the sales, 10% is set aside every day to be allocated as an external source of funds to finance the school's education.

The process of managing funds by student cooperatives is carried out with the aim of managing and allocating funds collected from cooperative members effectively and efficiently. This process begins with the collection of funds from cooperative members through monthly or annual contributions. The collected funds are then deposited in a cooperative account and managed by a cooperative committee consisting of several cooperative members selected based on their quality and commitment [10].

After the funds are collected and stored, the cooperative committee then allocates the funds for various cooperative purposes. This fund allocation is done based on the priorities and needs of the cooperative, such as operational costs, investment costs, and social assistance costs. In addition, the cooperative committee also supervises and reports on the use of funds to ensure that funds are used appropriately and transparently. Thus, the process of managing funds by student cooperatives can help improve the quality of services and increase cooperative members' trust in the organization [11].

C. Benefits of Student Cooperative-Based Financing

Student cooperative-based financing has a range of significant benefits in the context of education in public primary schools. First, student cooperatives help develop entrepreneurial and financial management skills early on, providing valuable practical experience for students. Second, cooperatives can strengthen school finances by providing an additional source of funding that is self-sustaining and sustainable. In addition, student cooperatives also support the well-being of their members and the school community at large, by providing more accessible and affordable financial services. Through cooperatives, students also learn about the values of cooperation, responsibility, and solidarity, which are important parts of students' character development [9].

Cooperative-based education financing has a significant positive impact on students. One of the main benefits is the early development of entrepreneurship and financial management skills. Through active involvement in student cooperatives, they learn about fund management, financial planning and responsible business practices. This not only enriches their knowledge but also prepares them for a more prosperous future financially independent. In addition, student cooperatives create a supportive environment for collaborative learning, where students can work together to achieve a common goal, increasing the sense of responsibility and solidarity among them [10].

For schools, student cooperatives act as a sustainable and self-sustaining source of additional funding. It assists schools in reducing dependence on external funds and

allows them to finance various educational activities and programs more flexibly. In addition, the existence of student cooperatives can increase the involvement of the school community, including teachers, parents, and the surrounding community, in supporting and utilizing cooperative services. Thus, student cooperatives not only support the financial stability of schools, but also strengthen the relationship between schools and their communities, creating a more inclusive and sustainable educational environment [4].

Student cooperatives play an important role in developing students' entrepreneurial skills. Through the cooperative, students are actively involved in various business activities, such as financial record-keeping, product marketing, and inventory management, all of which provide practical experience in the business world. This participation helps foster an entrepreneurial spirit early on, teaching students about responsibility, discipline, and teamwork. In addition, students learn to innovate and think creatively in the face of daily business challenges, which is very useful for their future. With these skills, students are not only prepared to become competent workers, but also have the potential to become successful entrepreneurs in the future [12].

D. Challenges in Implementation

The implementation of school cooperative-based financing management faces a number of significant operational challenges. One of the main obstacles is the lack of understanding and managerial skills among students and school staff involved in the cooperative. This limitation can hinder effective and efficient financial management and cause problems in budget planning and monitoring the use of funds. In addition, school cooperatives often lack supporting infrastructure and resources, such as adequate information technology systems for financial recording and reporting, which can result in inaccurate data and difficulties in strategic decision-making [13].

From a managerial perspective, another challenge is to ensure the involvement and active participation of all cooperative members, including students, teachers, and parents. Awareness and commitment to running a cooperative with the right principles is often low, requiring more efforts for continuous education and training. In addition, school cooperatives also have to deal with bureaucratic and regulatory issues that can slow down the decision-making process and program implementation. Management must be able to navigate the various government regulations and policies relating to cooperatives and education, and find ways to maintain transparency and accountability in the management of funds [6].

The response from schools and parents regarding the implementation of student cooperatives in schools is generally positive. Schools are fully supportive as cooperatives can be an effective means of developing students' entrepreneurial and managerial skills, as well as promoting the values of cooperation and responsibility. Parents also tend to respond favorably as they see direct benefits in terms of providing goods and services at more affordable prices as well as an opportunity to teach their children about the

importance of financial management and economics from an early age. In addition, the commitment of parents to increase the amount of savings in the cooperative shows their awareness and support of the cooperative's role in helping to finance education and school capital.

CONCLUSION

This research reveals that the management of student cooperative-based education financing in public primary schools has many positive impacts on students and schools. Student cooperatives are able to become an alternative source of financing that helps ease the school's financial burden and facilitate various educational activities. In addition, student cooperatives also play an important role in developing students' entrepreneurial skills, raising awareness of the importance of cooperation and responsibility, and nurturing an entrepreneurial spirit from an early age.

However, this study also found some challenges in its implementation. On the operational side, difficulties in financial management and limited human resources are the main obstacles. Meanwhile, managerial challenges include a lack of training for cooperative managers and a lack of support from external parties. Nevertheless, with a strong commitment from all relevant parties, student cooperatives can continue to grow and make a significant contribution to improving the quality of education in public primary schools.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Komariyah, N. Nurhidayah, N. Andriyana, and N. H. Murtafi'ah, "MANAJEMEN PEMBIAYAAN PENDIDIKAN YANG EFEKTIF UNTUK MENINGKATKAN MUTU PENDIDIKAN," *alwildan*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 78–86, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.57146/alwildan.v1i2.671.
- [2] A. Aslindah and W. G. Mulawarman, "Membangun Masa Depan Melalui Manajemen Keuangan Pendidikan yang Efektif," *impian j.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 65–74, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.30872/jimpian.v2i2.2606.
- [3] Muchamad Zainal Muttaqin, S. Ratnaningsi, and I. Purwanto, "Manajemen Pembiayaan Pendidikan Dalam Meningkatkan Mutu Pendidikan Di MTS Ummul Quro Al-Islami Bogor," *JTM*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 249–261, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.30997/jtm.v7i2.9478.
- [4] M. Muspawi and M. Lukita, "Pengelolaan Pembiayaan Pendidikan di Sekolah Dasar," *lectura*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 99–110, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.31849/lectura.v14i1.12237.
- [5] S. Suyitno, G. Abdullah, and N. A. N. Murniati, "Manajemen Pembiayaan Pendidikan Pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19 Sekolah Dasar Negeri," *J. Prakarsa Paedagogia*, vol. 5, no. 2, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.24176/jpp.v5i2.7988.
- [6] I. C. Edy, S. Marsono, and H. B. Utama, "Pemberdayaan Koperasi Siswa SMK Pembangunan Nasional Sukoharjo Dalam Rangka Optimalisasi Potensi Daerah

- yang Dapat Digunakan Untuk Membangun Kemandirian Ekonomi,” *wasananyata*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 124–130, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.36587/wasananyata.v4i2.747.
- [7] T. Susanti, “Manajemen Pembiayaan Sekolah Penggerak: Studi Deskriptif Kualitatif di SD Negeri 08 Kabawetan,” *GUAU Jurnal Pendidikan Profesi Guru Agama Islam*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 319–324, 2021.
- [8] R. P. Sukirman, A. Apriana, and R. Mutiah, “ANALISIS PERBANDINGAN MANAJEMEN PEMBIAYAAN KOPERASI SYARIAH DAN KOPERASI KONVENSIONAL TERHADAP PEREKONOMIAN DI KECAMATAN SUBANG,” *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 77–88, 2024.
- [9] B. Junedi, I. G. T. Isa, F. A. Baqi, A. Hidayat, S. Surtini, and I. Laela, “Pendampingan Kapasitas Siswa melalui Budaya Entrepreneurship di Koperasi Siswa di MA Al Khairiyah Pipitan,” *Jur. Inov. Pengab. & Pembed. Masy. (JIPPM)*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 39–50, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.54082/jipm.18.
- [10] U. N. Badriyatul Fitri, M. F. N. J. Latief, I. Bukhori, and A. Hidayat, “Manajemen Pembiayaan Pendidikan Berbasis Koperasi Pondok Pesantren,” *JTM*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 69, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.30997/jtm.v5i1.3812.
- [11] M. Minullah, “MEMBERDAYAKAN KOPERASI SEKOLAH DI MADRASAH IBTIDAIYAH NEGERI 1 SITUBONDO UNTUK MENINGKATKAN KESEJAHTERAAN PESERTA DIDIK,” *integritas*, vol. 4, no. 2, p. 199, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.36841/integritas.v4i2.779.
- [12] S. Dewi, “STRATEGI PENINGKATAN SUMBER DANA DALAM PEMBIAYAAN PENDIDIKAN DI SMK NEGERI 3 SALATIGA,” Feb. 13, 2020. doi: 10.31219/osf.io/kp57f.
- [13] L. Rifai, R. Abdullah, and N. H. Murtafiah, “PENGEMBANGAN MANAJEMEN PEMBIAYAAN PENDIDIKAN BERBASIS KOPERASI PELAJAR DI PONDOK PESANTREN,” *UNISAN JURNAL: JURNAL MANAJEMEN DAN PENDIDIKAN*, vol. 01, no. 03, pp. 262–268, 2022.